

D1.3 REPORT ON POLICY-MAKING EVENT

WP1.

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D1.3 REPORT ON POLICY-MAKING EVENT

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS¹

Concept	Definition
Health Literacy (HL)	HL entails people’s knowledge and competences to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information to make judgments and decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention and health promotion (1).
Digital HL (dHL)	dHL is the ability to seek, find, understand, and appraise health information from electronic sources and apply the knowledge gained to addressing or solving a health problem (2).
(d)HL	HL and dHL
European Union	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden.
Beyond EU	Australia, Canada, New Zealand, United Kingdom (England, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales), United States of America.
Social Innovation	Social innovation refers to the design and implementation of new solutions that imply conceptual, process, product, or organisational change, which ultimately aim to improve the welfare and wellbeing of individuals and communities. Many initiatives undertaken by the social economy and by the civil society have proven to be innovative in dealing with socio-economic and environmental problems, while contributing to economic development. To fully tap the potential of social innovation, an enabling policy framework is needed to support public, non-profit, and private actors to co-construct and implement socially innovative solutions and thereby contribute to address socio-economic issues, build stronger territorial resilience, and better respond to future shocks (6).
Best practice	A best practice is a relevant policy or intervention implemented in a real-life setting and which has been favourably assessed in terms of adequacy (ethics and evidence) and equity as well as effectiveness and efficiency related to process and outcomes. Other criteria are important for a successful transferability of the practice such as a clear definition of the context, sustainability, cross-sectional, and participation of stakeholders (8).
Monitoring and evaluation tools, methods, and frameworks	Monitoring and evaluation tools, methods, and frameworks in (d)HL that are validated and published in peer-reviewed journals; they measure/quantify individuals’ (d)HL (9) and organizations’ HL and (d)HL environments covering different target populations and services (e.g., the HLS-EU questionnaire, the eHL Assessment toolkit (eHLA) and the eHL Questionnaire (eHLQ), the M-POHL network action or the WHO HL Road Map).

¹ To maintain uniformity at Project level, acronyms and terminology were agreed on by the whole Consortium during technical project meetings. The definitions used in this table were developed in Project Deliverable D1.1 Report on (d)HL.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

IDEAHL – **Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living** is a Coordination and Support Action financed by Horizon Europe. It aims at developing and testing new models and approaches of digital health literacy intervention development and application through the co-creation of a comprehensive and inclusive EU digital health literacy Strategy.

The IDEAHL Strategy encompasses the formulation of policies promoting (d)HL, the recommendation and testing of interventions supporting (d)HL, and the monitoring of valid (d)HL indicators across Europe. It supports the development of the necessary competencies to achieve a sufficient level of (d)HL, while relating it with recent developments in society regarding health, digital technology use, civic engagement, and sociocultural and socioeconomic trends.

As policymakers' validation is considered pivotal to maintain the long-term sustainability of the project's outcomes, they were selected as a key target group to identify potential areas of improvements of the Strategy and to ensure its endorsement and support from Member States. The European Parliament was selected as the location of the event, co-sponsored by WHO/Europe.

The event was devised following three main objectives:

1. to engage and commit policymakers in supporting the (d)HL Strategy at EU level
2. to identify potential areas of improvement for developing the Strategy
3. to support the next co-creation and implementation activities related to the Strategy

For this reason, the Brussels event was organised around three core thematic areas:

1. presentation of (d)HL mapping results
2. exchange of experiences
3. co-creation of the (d)HL Strategy

The event had a total of **133** registered participants of which 69 attended via online modalities.

1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

This report outlines the results of the IDEAHL policymakers' event (Task 1.5) with the final aim of supporting the co-creation and endorsement of the project's (d)HL Strategy.

The IDEAHL Strategy encompasses the formulation of policies promoting (d)HL, the recommendation and testing of interventions supporting (d)HL, and the monitoring of valid (d)HL indicators across Europe. It supports the development of the necessary competencies to achieve a sufficient level of (d)HL, while relating it with recent developments in society regarding health, digital technology use, civic engagement, and sociocultural and socioeconomic trends.

This work is based on the experiences gathered during the preparatory phase of the event (project months 6 to 10)— framing it within the adopted methodology fostering stakeholders' engagement in support of the project's comprehensive and inclusive EU strategy for improving (d)HL. It was written in the context of the activities planned in Work Package 1 "Map health literacy research and practices in Europe and beyond" addressing the interconnection between (d)HL and the health and well-being of EU citizens.

In the initial stage of the project— IDEAHL strengthened its knowledge base by mapping (d)HL research, policies, projects, and existing practices in Europe and beyond². Specific attention was paid to existing literature and knowledge about the key citizen groups considered by IDEAHL, along with gender dimension, social innovation, ethics and privacy, and inclusiveness.

The Central European Initiative - Executive Secretariat is the project partner in charge of Task 1.5 which aims to engage and commit policymakers in supporting the Strategy— fostering long-term commitment and support from Member States for the activities related to the Strategy.

² Results can be found in Project Deliverable D1.1 Report on (d)HL.

2. METHODOLOGY

The following chapter defines the methodology adopted for the organisation of the IDEAHL policymakers' event at the European Parliament in Brussels. The *first section* presents the event's scope and objectives— accounting for the selection of policymakers as the main target group to be involved in the activities. The *second section* illustrates the steps taken to maximise stakeholders' participation and engagement during the event. The *third section* concerns the definition of the event's programme and activities. The section also illustrates some of the presented content focused on gauging policymakers' interest— highlighting the value position of the IDEAHL project to the audience. The defined methodology is framed around all relevant Work Packages and related Tasks.

2.1. SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES

Following its set objectives, the IDEAHL project aims at achieving significant and concrete impact in the promotion of healthier lifestyles and better health at EU level. Thus, the project addresses not only EU citizens; but also, all relevant stakeholders at political, national, and EU level— engaging selected target groups in project's activities, as well as keeping them informed on project outcomes, uncovered priorities, barriers, and best practices and policies in support of (d)HL.

In this regard, the IDEAHL project is co-creating a Strategy at EU level to develop and test new models and approaches of (d)HL intervention development and application. The Strategy focuses on health promotion, disease prevention, treatment, and self-care. As policymakers' validation is considered pivotal to maintain the long-term sustainability of project's outcomes, they were selected as a key target group to identify potential areas of improvements of the Strategy and to ensure its endorsement and support from Member States.

With this clear objective in mind, it was considered essential for the Brussels event to provide a comprehensive outlook on the IDEAHL approach and methodology— and the actions taken insofar— while aiming to support knowledge exchange among participants. By bringing together policymakers, representatives of national and regional authorities and other organisations across Europe, the Brussels event also aimed to support the development of the Strategy by uncovering

potential solutions leading to citizens' empowerment and by fostering long-term results from the IDEAHL project in Europe and beyond.

Moreover, to maximise its impact in promoting better health management and interaction with healthcare professionals across Europe, the Strategy was envisioned to account for geographic, social, and economic determinants of inequities in (d)HL. For this reason, the involvement of policymakers was envisaged to help addressing and defining the main dimensions and related approaches to be considered during the planning and the implementation of (d)HL strategies at country level and implementation actions, locally, towards citizens and the ones at main risk of exclusion. The complete concept and programme of the event can be found in Annex 5.1 Concept and Agenda.

The three thematic areas of the Brussels event can be summarised as follows:

1 – Presentation of (d)HL mapping results: the IDEAHL Consortium has worked extensively to develop an inclusive mapping of the literature concerning (d)HL in Europe and beyond. The activity lays the foundations of the Strategy, and it will provide an illustration of (d)HL in Europe and beyond. Participants will receive comprehensive information on the methodology, approach and future developments.

2 – Exchange of experiences: knowledge sharing on how to empower European citizens in regards of d(HL) is a key component of the Strategy. Participants will be involved in the identification of obstacles, difficulties, and areas of improvement of the Strategy. In this regard, the event also represents an opportunity for networking activities and future collaboration.

3 – Co-creation of the (d)HL Strategy: the involvement of policymakers represents a key element for the success of the project and the Strategy to be developed. A roadmap for the IDEAHL co-creation experience will be presented to participants. Moreover, a dedicated co-creation workshop will be offered in the afternoon session to volunteering policy makers to provide ideas, experiences and good practices on (d)HL to contribute to the construction of the future (d)HL Strategy.

2.2. STAKEHOLDERS' PARTICIPATION AND ENGAGEMENT

In line with the project's *Dissemination Strategy (D.5.1)*, the I-CEE Identifying, Connecting, Engaging, and Enabling Stakeholder Engagement Approach was adapted to be utilised by the IDEAHL project. This methodology consists of four stages, which collectively have the aim of identifying and engaging with potential multipliers i.e., stakeholders who can directly and indirectly increase levels of engagement and take up with the project:

In this regard, to maximise its impact in engaging policymakers, the European Parliament was selected as the preferred location of the Brussels' event. Thanks to the support of the Friuli Venezia Giulia Region, the meeting was hosted at the EU Parliament and publicised via their internal channels— allowing for higher visibility and reach, as well as expected engagement from participants.

In addition, the event was promoted via CEI's institutional channels to maximise its visibility and increase participation of relevant stakeholders. For this purpose, a section dedicated to the event was posted on CEI website— a save the date to register to the event was promoted also through CEI social media channels.

Also, to guarantee the expected number of policymakers, it was decided to open the meeting to online participation to the morning sessions³. Moreover, interpreting services— translating to Spanish, French, German and Italian— were also offered to all participants to foster participation. In addition, in consideration of their multiple appointments, the scope and purpose of the event was sent to all active Members of Parliament (MEPs) (as of February 2023)— providing a detailed overview of the different sections of the event to foster participation in accordance with policymakers' particular schedule and/or interests. A White Paper providing a detailed overview

³ The afternoon co-creation session was limited to in-presence participation only, due to the highly interactive nature of the activity.

of the IDEAHL project was also prepared by the Consortium to support online communications and invitations to the event (see Annex 5.2)

Furthermore, the WHO Office for Europe recently launched the Regional digital health action plan for the WHO European Region 2023–2030. It aims to support countries in leveraging and scaling up digital transformation for better health and in aligning digital technology investment decisions with their health system needs. Digital Health Literacy is one of the considered strategic objectives— urging Member States to foster the digital health literacy of health workers and citizens and to enhance their skills through digital health literacy programmes.

Therefore, to further promote the IDEAHL event, in its early preparation stage, communication and coordination efforts between the WHO/Europe and the CEI led to the event being co-sponsored by the WHO/Europe— also resulting in additional dissemination via their official channels and with the Office overseeing the keynote speech of the event.

2.3. PROGRAMME AND ACTIVITIES

The opening session of the event comprised the welcoming and introductory statements from selected project partners’ representatives and external stakeholders. The event started with the institutional greetings from Ms. Elena Lizzi, Member of the European Parliament for North-East Italy, who promoted and facilitated its organisation in the EP. The speakers opening the event depicted a high-level representation of key relevant organisations capable of providing valuable insight on the importance of (d)HL literacy for the wellbeing of all EU citizens⁴.

The next session was envisioned as an introduction aiming to set the framework for participants. It presented the IDEAHL project, illustrated the results achieved within WP1 activities, and introduced the development of the IDEAHL Strategy to policymakers. In addition, a short Q&A session was implemented allowing for all necessary clarification to be addressed.

⁴ The list of speakers can be found in the event programme (Annex 5.1).

To clarify, the first presentation provided a general overview of the IDEAHL Project— comprising the consortium, its objectives, intended target audiences, and core activities. It then focused on the IDEAHL value proposition to highlight to policymakers the strengths of the project’s framework and overall approach, e.g. its focus on social innovation and co-creation, its special attention on gender, equality, ethics and privacy.

To contextualise the results achieved insofar by project partners, a dedicated session on how the consortium has addressed the uncovered (d)HL related barriers was included. In this regard, focus was placed on how to effectively promote knowledge exchange and facilitate the long-term implementation of (d)HL related initiatives and policies.

Furthermore, in line with the event’s objective of fostering commitment from policymakers in the Project, the presentation highlighted the long-term impact of the activities implemented insofar— drawing attention to the IDEAHL health literacy Atlas (T1.4), the network of identified (d)HL practices in EU and Beyond, and pilot initiatives, as well as the envisaged co-creation workshops, exercises, and consultations. The presentation ended with an illustration of the expected long-term benefits of the Project— remarking how IDEAHL’s outputs are designed to support the actual well-being of EU citizens, especially if endorsed by EU policymakers.

The second presentation addressed the results of the first round of activities concerning the findings from the mapping of (d)HL research and practices in Europe and beyond (WP1). The presentation highlighted the importance of using evidence-based interventions and including demographic, social, cultural and gender aspects when promoting (d)HL. It was also clarified that the identification of target groups in need of (d)HL interventions can be considered a priority, especially for policymakers. In this regard, marginalised populations appear not to be sufficiently represented in the mapped literature— further remarking the importance of the IDEAHL’s project value proposition.

Aims and results of WP1-related tasks (T1.1, T1.2, T1.3) provided methodological insight and highlighted important elements of interventions on the analysed literature on (d)HL research and practices in Europe and beyond. In this regard, concerning (d)HL interventions at policy level, it informed that the addressed literature frequently addressed the need for a system transformation. The presentation highlighted the importance of cross-sectoral interventions to

increase (d)HL and of addressing multiple settings and policy areas. Furthermore, determining HL at population level— before and after intervention— appears to be crucial to effectively identify target groups in need of support. The presentation ended with additional recommendations and guidelines at strategic level, for best practices, as well as for monitoring and evaluation purposes.

The last presentation of the first session informed policymakers about co-creation activities and their application for policy making. By addressing the merits of co-creating the (d)HL Strategy, the IDEAHL approach to co-creation was presented to stakeholders— fostering the long-term engagement of policymakers in building strong collective knowledge for the wellbeing of all EU citizens.

The speakers remarked the value of the co-creation process as a means to achieve target and result oriented outcomes, focused on the following main areas of intervention: health promotion, disease prevention, treatment, and self-care. In this regard, policymakers were encouraged to engage in future co-creation activities, to review the upcoming drafts of the IDEAHL Strategy and to be part of the project online (d)HL panel and answer to the IDEAHL EU Survey. Policymakers' engagement was supported by additional Project's exploitable results, i.e. the replicable methodology for planning and implementing co-creation for healthcare related policies/strategies, the wide EU-based awareness raising campaign about (d)HL, importance, opportunities, and best practices, as well as the analysis of the co-creation experience and lessons learnt for other comparable activities⁵.

In the next session, the representative from the World Health Organization, regional office for Europe, gave the event's keynote speech. It provided valuable insight to policymakers, addressing DH literacy in the European region. It illustrated actions to improve dHL in all settings at regional and national level, as well as providing methodological and practical information on leveraging and scaling up digital transformation for better health and resilience in the European region⁶. The presentation ended with recommendations to support (d)HL policymaking— including the adoption of a patient-centred approach that fosters public trust and protects privacy rights; the

⁵ For additional, more in depth information, please see Project Deliverable 'Report on (d)HL WP1' (D1.1).

⁶ Because the data presented by WHO/Europe at the event are currently under review (as of April 2023), and are therefore to be considered confidential, it was decided not to cite them in the Deliverable to avoid potential misinterpretations.

integration of digital health into healthcare education to equip the workforce with essential digital skills; and the adoption of all capacity-building efforts to promote digital health training as an integral and sustainable part of workforce development.

The following session dedicated to exchanging experiences with policymakers was framed around the following main topics: citizens' empowerment, best practices, policies, funding instruments, barriers, and challenges. It aimed at engaging policymakers by presenting the valuable experience and knowledge of selected experts from some of the IDEAHL Project countries. In consideration of the target aim of the deliverable, the information and results presented to policymakers will not be summarized in this chapter. The list of experts can be found in Annex 5.1, while the main topics and areas of interest addressed by policymakers during the event can be found in the following chapters (3. Results).

The afternoon co-creation workshop with policymakers had the specific objectives of creating potential future collaborations between participants, while gathering initial feedback on one introductory question and on two specific domains of the (d)HL Strategy, as per the methodology presented in Project Deliverable D2.1. At the beginning, moderators explained to the participants how the co-creation activities were going to be conducted— remarking on the importance of selecting policymakers as a key target group for the co-creation of the Strategy.

The 24 participants were evenly divided into three groups, according to their expected experience and knowledge in (d)HL. The core activity was brainstorming ideas regarding envisaged challenges and barriers on (d)HL implementation. The main tool used was a physical board divided into 4 different areas: legal and administrative barriers, individual and societal barriers, healthcare related barriers, and budgetary gaps. After a first discussion about the expected barriers for each area, some of the participants changed groups to further complement the gathered information and to account for additional perspectives. Key information was summarized on the board and presented by moderators to all participants.

The level of participation from stakeholders can be considered high— leading to the collection of valuable input for the strategy and potential new collaboration between engaged stakeholders and the IDEAHL consortium. The results of the activity are summarised in the next chapter.

3. RESULTS

The event had a total of 133 registered participants of which 69 attended via online modalities. The signature sheet indicates that at least 53 participants were present at the EU Parliament— also counting IDEAHL project partners⁷. As an approach, even partial participation of policymakers was considered sufficient and a starting point to foster their interest in later Project activities to capitalise on mid- and long-term stakeholders’ engagement⁸. Complementarily, 34 online participants indicated their willingness to participate in future IDEAHL co-creation activities.

It is important to highlight that the Policymakers’ event was envisaged as a single step in a longer process with the ultimate objective of ensuring support for the IDEAHL (d)HL Strategy at EU level. In this regard, the Brussels event is to be considered one concrete step in the longer policymakers’ engagement process— to be complemented by the upcoming co-creation and implementation activities related to the Strategy.

Following on this, as per the nature of the event, objective indicators to measure engagement and interest from policymakers are difficult to produce at this stage. Therefore, the content discussed by policymakers during the whole event can help demonstrate the achievement of all set objectives.

First, concerning the IDEAHL methodology, policymakers have demonstrated particular interest in the IDEAHL support to (d)HL evidence-based interventions. Furthermore, the inclusion of demographic, social, cultural and gender aspects in (d)HL, as well as IDEAHL special attention to gender, equality, ethics, and privacy was particularly well-received— especially as it is directly linked to the necessary support of more vulnerable and marginalised populations. In line with the favoured approach fostering inclusion of cross-sectoral interventions addressing multiple settings

⁷ For additional information on the event’s participants see Annex 5.3

⁸ For additional clarifications see the methodology chapter of this Deliverable (2.1 Scope and objectives)

and policy areas, the event managed to promote the IDEAHL specific value proposition to policymakers. The list of methodological aspects addressed during the event can be found here below:

- Replicable methodology
- Recommendations and guidelines at strategic level
- Focus on social innovation
- Support of (d)HL evidence-based interventions
- Identification of target groups in need of (d)HL interventions
- Focus on marginalised populations
- Inclusion demographic, social, cultural and gender aspects in (d)HL
- Special attention to gender, equality, ethics and privacy
- Promotion of knowledge exchange supporting (d)HL policy development
- Inclusion of cross-sectoral interventions for multiple settings/policy areas

Second, regarding the dissemination of Project's activities, policymakers have confirmed their interest in the IDEAHL (d)HL Strategy at EU level. Complementary initiatives mentioned during the event include the IDEAHL health literacy Atlas, and the network of identified (d)HL practices in EU and Beyond. The involvement of policymakers in future co-creation workshops has been clearly highlighted on different occasions throughout the morning sessions— with the introductory co-creation exercise being held in the afternoon. Furthermore, the importance of IDEAHL helping to raise awareness on (d)HL to EU citizens— as well as its focus on effectively communicating lessons learnt during the activities— was particularly appreciated. The list of mentioned activities can be found here below:

- IDEAHL health literacy Atlas
- Network of identified (d)HL practices in EU and Beyond
- Co-creation workshops
- Review the upcoming drafts of the IDEAHL Strategy
- Project online (d)HL panel
- IDEAHL EU Survey
- EU-based awareness raising campaign about (d)HL
- Development of comprehensive lessons learnt from the project and similar activities

Third, on the content discussed during the event, it is possible to highlight the policymakers' main areas of interest. As citizens' empowerment can be considered a priority for initiatives fostering (d)HL, special attention to minorities and vulnerable groups cannot be disregarded. Ageing and demographic changes need to be included in the main population groups— with solutions aiming to reduce the generational digital divide. In addition, particular focus was given on the challenges related to measuring (d)HL and the relation between d)HL and the actual wellbeing of the population. The below list outlines the main topics discussed at the event:

- Citizens' empowerment
- Capacity-building efforts to promote digital health training
- Correlation between (d)HL and citizens wellbeing
- Mental health literacy
- dHL and increased access to healthcare service delivery
- (d)HL and health promoting behaviour
- Ageing and demographic changes
- Digital divide
- Telemedicine and New Care Technologies
- Integration of digital health into healthcare education
- Measuring instrument and (d)HL evaluation

Finally, to help uncover potential areas of improvement, the co-creation session was specifically targeted toward barriers and challenges to (d)HL implementation. The discussion was centred around legal administrative barriers; budgetary gaps; healthcare related barriers; and individual and societal barriers. The detailed list of addressed topics can be found here below:

Legal administrative barriers

- Privacy and legal issues
- Administrative blockage
- Insufficient safe infrastructures
- Difficulties in legal/administrative systems - "make it simpler, keep it safe"
- Need to simplify the interface between human and technology
- Low credibility of citizens towards the government compared to the one they have towards private companies
- Insufficient harmonisation of rules across regions/countries
- Low connection of stakeholders

- Low integration of digital innovation in care services
- Complex primary structure

Budgetary gaps

- No specific budget for (d)HL - it is not at the top of the agenda
- Lack of sustainability for scale-up and integration of approaches
- Socio-economic disparities (resources of each individual/geographical area)
- Infrastructure barriers

Healthcare related barriers

- No cross-sectional/interdisciplinary collaboration
- Lack of education of informal caregivers
- Resistance to change
- Need for a user-friendly interface (considering age)
- Healthcare overburdened due to Covid19
- Rapid changes in technology

Individual/societal barriers

- Digital tools are not adapted to end-users
- Lack of motivation (“you don’t need what you don’t know”)
- Lack of trust in the information online.
- Low digital media literacy
- Digital shame
- Ageism
- Lack of consideration of the specific needs of some target groups (e.g. older people, people living in remote areas)
- Too much information - don't know which is reliable
- Low digital skills of citizens/professionals/policymakers
- Low marketability of the dHL concept

4. CONCLUSIONS

Due to the timeframe of project activities, it is important to highlight that the Policymakers' event was envisaged as one step in the longer process of policymakers' engagement to be complemented by the upcoming co-creation and implementation activities related to the Strategy. For this reason, aside from the number of policymakers attending the event, it is early to measure the engagement and interest of policymakers in project activities at this stage.

Nonetheless, following the event's three core objectives, the policymakers already provided inputs beneficial to the Strategy throughout the whole event. Moreover, they demonstrated high interest in the mentioned project activities— as well as the Project's methodology and value proposition. That said the setting at the EU Parliament; the partnership with WHO/Europe; and the high-level experts involved as speakers all contributed to both increased networking opportunities, and to reaching a higher level of expected involvement of policymakers in future IDEAHL activities. For this reason, it is possible to consider the level of participation from the target group as high— with the number of participating policymakers being defined as acceptable.

In the end, in line with the project's objectives, it is important to mention that the Policymakers' event in Brussels can be considered as an effective first step to foster the involvement of the identified actors to be carried out throughout the whole project implementation.

5. ANNEXES

- ANNEX I – CONCEPT AND AGENDA
- ANNEX II – WHITE PAPER
- ANNEX III – PARTICIPANTS
- ANNEX IV - PICTURES

ANNEX I - CONCEPT AND AGENDA

BUILDING AN IDEAHL EUROPE

High-Level Policymaking Event to Develop a European (Digital) Health Literacy Strategy

SCOPE AND PROGRAMME

7 March 2023
Brussels, Belgium

REGISTER NOW: <https://forms.gle/iJ9CayBH8JE8mrvUA>

SCOPE AND PURPOSE

Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL), funded by the Horizon Europe programme of the European Commission, is a project with the ultimate objective of empowering EU citizens in using digital tools and taking a more active role in the management of their own health and well-being, as well as supporting innovations for coordinated person-centered care models.

For this reason, IDEAHL is developing and testing new models and approaches of (digital) health literacy intervention development and application through the co-creation of a (d)HL Strategy at European level. The Strategy focuses on health promotion, disease prevention, treatment and (self-)care. To maximize its impact in promoting healthier lifestyles, better health management and interaction with healthcare professionals across Europe, the Strategy considers geographic, social, and economic determinants of inequities in (d)HL. Moreover, the project adopts a truly bottom-up approach by ensuring wide stakeholders' involvement.

As strategic partnerships and collaboration with policy makers are essential for ensuring the success of the project, **a high-level policymaking event has been organized to support the (d)HL Strategy at European level, in Brussels.** The Consortium will present the preliminary findings from the IDEAHL activities and present its roadmap for the co-creation of the Strategy together with stakeholders and citizens from the 10 partner countries. The aim is to ensure policy making support for the Strategy's development and long-term sustainability.

In the initial stage of the project, IDEAHL strengthened its knowledge base by mapping (d)HL research, policies, projects, and existing practices in Europe and beyond. Specific attention was paid on existing literature and knowledge about the key citizen groups considered by IDEAHL, along with gender dimension, social innovation, ethics and privacy, and inclusiveness.

To complement the mapping of (d)HL, representatives of practice from healthcare and social services— as well as citizens in general— will be involved in a large co-creation exercise in the 10 partner countries to identify and discuss obstacles, difficulties, and areas of improvement related with (d)HL, eventually supporting the development of an (d)HL Strategy at European level. In addition, a network of key stakeholders for the promotion of (d) HL across the EU (and beyond) to foster exchange and uptake of best practices will also be developed.

The event is co-sponsored by the WHO Office for Europe that has recently launched the Regional digital health action plan for the WHO European Region 2023–2030. Digital Health Literacy is a strategic objective of the action plan, with a clear reference also in the resolution that urges Member States to “measuring the digital health literacy of health workers and citizens and enhancing their skills through digital health literacy programmes”.

The event will therefore provide a comprehensive outlook on the IDEAHL approach and methodology, and the actions taken insofar, while also aiming to facilitate knowledge exchange. By bringing together policymakers, representatives of national and regional authorities and other organizations across

Europe, the event aims to support the development of the Strategy strengthening the commitment toward citizens' empowerment and ensuring long-term results from IDEAHL in Europe and beyond.

OBJECTIVES

1 – **Presentation of (d)HL mapping results:** the IDEAHL Consortium has worked extensively to develop a comprehensive mapping of the literature concerning (d)HL in Europe and beyond. The activity lays the foundations of the Strategy, and it will provide an illustration of (d)HL in Europe and beyond. Information concerning the methodology, approach and future developments will also be shared.

2 – **Exchange of experiences:** knowledge sharing on how to empower European citizen in regards of d(HL) is a key component of the Strategy. Participants will be involved in the identification of obstacles, difficulties, and areas of improvement. In this regard, the event also represents an opportunity for networking activities and future collaboration.

3 – **Co-creation of the (d)HL Strategy:** the involvement of policymakers represents a key element for the success of the project and the Strategy to be developed. A roadmap for the IDEAHL co-creation experience will be presented to participants. Moreover, a dedicated co-creation workshop will be offered in the afternoon session to volunteering policy makers to provide ideas, experiences and good practices on (d)HL to contribute to the construction of the future (d)HL Strategy

PARTICIPANTS

Policymakers, representatives of national and regional authorities and other organizations across Europe.

AGENDA

Building an IDEAHL Europe

*European Parliament, Brussels
Room: SPINELLI 5E2*

7 March 2023

9:00 – 9:15

Registration

9:15 – 9:45

Opening and Introductory statements

- *Elena Lizzi, Member of the European Parliament for North-East Italy, European Parliament*
- *Nina Kodelja, Deputy Secretary General, Central European Initiative*
- *Natasha Azzopardi-Muscat, Director, Division of Country Health Policies and Systems, World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe*
- *Irina Kalderon, Policy Officer of DG CNECT, European Commission*

9:45 - 10:45

Moderator: Gian Matteo Apuzzo

Presenting IDEAHL

- Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living: General overview of the project
Marta Pisano González, Head of Centered Care Service, General Direction of Care and Social Healthcare, Ministry of Health, Asturias, Spain
- Mapping (d)HL research and practices in Europe and beyond
Charlotte Brun Thorup, Research consultant, Docent, University College of Northern Denmark
- Co-creation of the EU strategy to improve (d)HL
Beatrice Avagnina, Managing Director, Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation & Adele De Stefani, Project Manager, Istituto per Servizi di Ricovero e Assistenza agli Anziani
- Q&A - 15 minutes

10:45 – 11:15

Coffee break

11:15 – 11:50

Keynote Presentation

- Digital health literacy in the European region
David Novillo Ortiz, Unit Head / Regional Adviser, Data and Digital Health Division of Country Health Policies and Systems, World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe
- Discussion - 15 minutes

11:50 – 12:40

Moderator: Gian Matteo Apuzzo

Exchange of experiences

Topics: (digital) health literacy, citizens' empowerment, best practices, policies, funding instruments, barriers, and challenges

- The digital evolution of public health: Italian design methodology for improving telemedicine and Public Health Workforce professionals' skills
Francesco Gabbrielli, Director National Centre for Telemedicine and New Care Technologies, Italian Public Health Institute
Marco Simonelli, Scientific Secretariat, Italian Public Health Institute
- Promotion of general and mental health literacy among migrants in Sweden
Josefin Wångdahl, Assistant Professor, Aging Research Center, Karolinska Institutet Tomtebodavägen
- Experience from Puglia Region
Giuseppe Memola, Puglia Region/EUREGHA
- Digital health as a healthcare complementary tool in SEE
Mira Jovanovski Dasic, Secretariat Head, South-eastern Europe Health Network
- Moderated open discussion - 15 minutes

12:40 – 13:00

Conclusion and closing remarks

- IDEAHL next steps: support and endorsement of the (d)HL Strategy
Gian Matteo Apuzzo, Senior Programme Manager, Focal Point for Health Strategies and Emergencies response, Central European Initiative

13:00 – 14:00

Lunch

14:00 – 16:00

Moderator: Michelle Perello

Co-creation workshop with policy makers for (d)HL
Strategy – Consulta Europa [*Optional*]

- Introductory session – 30 minutes
- Co-creation session – 60 minutes
- Wrap-up and conclusions on co-created concepts – 30 minutes

The IDEAHL Consortium:

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ANNEX II - WHITEPAPER

Aiming at improving digital empowerment for active healthy living of citizens in Europe

IDEAHL

Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living

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DIGITAL HEALTH

Field of knowledge and practice associated with the development and use of digital technologies to improve health.

HEALTH LITERACY

People's knowledge and competency in accessing, understanding, appraising, and applying health information to make judgments and decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention and health promotion.[1]

DIGITAL HEALTH LITERACY

The ability to seek, find, understand, and appraise health information from electronic resources to make appropriate health decisions or solve a health problem.[2]

E-HEALTH

The use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in health products, services and processes, combined with organisational changes in healthcare systems and new skills, to improve citizens' health, efficiency, and productivity.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

HL = Health Literacy
dHL = digital Health Literacy
(d)HL = HL & dHL

Public and private health care-related expenses are increasing unsustainable. Digital health is rapidly developing as a solution to current and future health care problems by increasing access to information, services and products that help individuals better manage their own health. However, if an individual lacks the basic ability of how to find, comprehend, and apply that information through digital means – known as digital health literacy, or dHL – then these tools' and services' potential to improve self-management will be greatly reduced and the expected cost-effectiveness benefits will not be achieved.

The **Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL)** initiative is a Europe-wide effort that aims to create a comprehensive and inclusive EU strategy for improving dHL. Co-creation of health literacy policies and practices is the best way to achieve this, and the initiative will therefore engage over 1,300 stakeholders during its lifetime. As part of this, a network of champion practices, and pilots of promising practices will be initiated. A map of current dHL at country and regional levels will also be created, using validated monitoring mechanisms identified by the initiative. In this way, IDEAHL will help empower EU citizens in using digital tools to play a more active role in managing their own health and well-being, and support innovation for person-centred care models. All this will contribute to reigning over health-related expenses to sustainable levels. Stakeholder engagement is central to the initiative to achieve these outcomes.

[1] Sørensen et al, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-12-80>. [2] Norman et al, 2006, doi:10.2196/jmir.8.2.e9.

BACKGROUND

Digital health technologies are a driving force for helping citizens and health professionals address preventable risk factors associated with diseases. They can facilitate early detection and treatment and support healthy ageing. Digital health solutions are also key to support a shift in care provision by empowering citizens in accessing their personal health data and managing their own health.[3] The World Health Organization (WHO) states that a majority of its member states have an eHealth strategy, legislation to protect electronic patient data, and ongoing eHealth initiatives.[4] Despite these advancements – which have accelerated during the Covid-19 pandemic – the digital transformation of healthcare risks leaving behind the very people it hopes to empower.

This is because many individuals, both professionals and laypeople, lack a sufficient level of dHL. Being able to use technology is not the same as being knowledgeable or skilled in the use of technology to understand health issues and act accordingly. Vulnerable groups are particularly at risk of insufficient dHL, and professionals often lack training and support to identify this end-user groups.

The challenges already being faced in the deployment of digital health technologies are very likely to be coupled with under-use confusion over interpretation of results and recommendations, and even incorrect or harmful decision-making in the most serious cases.

The economic effects of this unrealized capacity in digital health could be devastating. Tools and services that aim to reduce the health care economic burden may end up increasing it. The significant costs associated with developing, implementing, and managing digital health technologies are instead added to existing health care costs, which do not decrease when many of its users fail to comprehend the technologies' intentions and outputs. It could simply make the situation worse instead of better.

We must therefore consider dHL as a “superdeterminant” of healthy decision-making in a digitalized society[5], as well as a critical factor in determining the success of many digital health technologies.

The evidence from the WHO's most comprehensive scoping reviews of equity in digital health technologies suggests digital literacy as a key driver of differences in access, use and engagement across equity domains.[6]

[3] EC, COM(2018) 233 on enabling the digital transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market [4]<https://www.who.int/health-topics/digital-health> [5] Kessel et al, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.invent.2022.100500>

[6] WHO (2022). Equity within digital health technology within the WHO European Region: a scoping review

Survival of the less-than-fittest

Digital health interventions that do not achieve their full potential due to insufficient use by low dHL groups, but nonetheless remain active over long periods, are called survivors. This stubbornly long lifespan is often motivated by the significant costs of developing and implementing such interventions. However, leaving them in place means they may often out-compete development of potentially more effective dHL-sensitive interventions in terms of infrastructure, resources, or even marketability.

The "patient" will not see you now

The EU Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) stipulates that all new digital health technologies under its jurisdiction must provide evidence of both pre- and post-market effectiveness to be compliant[7]. Low dHL among users puts this effectiveness at risk due to improper or insufficient use. This may lead to a lack of clinical or real-world evidence that can lead to technologies never reaching the market – or being removed from it.

Sceptics, unite

How users feel that their integrity is managed may also influence their use of digital health technologies. Lower dHL users use digital platforms with lower quality or misleading health management information more often than high dHL users[8]. Once established, removing such biases is difficult. It can result in effective digital health tools and sources not being used by groups that need them the most, or inappropriate tools and sources being used when they should not be.

Mind the (widening) health gap

Some digital health technologies may be successfully implemented or show effectiveness in groups with high dHL, but not in groups with low dHL. This can lead to improvements in the typically lower health care needs of high dHL groups, while having little or no effect on the significantly greater health care needs of low dHL groups. Health differences between high and low dHL groups will therefore increase. The cost of the technology may therefore not be outweighed by its benefits, with the equation becoming even more unbalanced over time.

An uphill battle

The dHL level of both professional and citizen users can affect the ease of which a digital health technology is implemented. Low dHL has been shown to increase resistance to technology use, regardless of its potential effectiveness. Professional users tend to disregard technologies with outputs they cannot interpret, and citizen users shun products and services that are not intuitively understandable.

#(d) Me too

There is a need to develop more inclusive and gender-responsive digital training that focuses on the specific needs of women. Although there is evidence indicating that in high-income countries women use the Internet more frequently than men to access health-related resources the majority of available tools do not address women's needs and priorities[9].

The **Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL)** initiative places this perspective at the forefront. Consisting of 14 research and practitioner organisations in 10 European countries and funded by the EU Horizon Healthy Citizens 2.0 framework, it puts dHL at the centre of EU health strategy. Together with over 1,300 stakeholders from public health and social services, technology branch representatives, civil society organisations, citizens, IDEAHL will co-create, test, and evaluate an inclusive and comprehensive EU strategy on dHL, which can be implemented at national and regional levels.

This strategy will involve the formulation of dHL-promoting policies, the recommendation and testing dHL-strengthening interventions, and the monitoring of valid dHL indicators across Europe. The target audiences of the strategy's activities are both at the professional level (who can develop, deploy, recommend, and prescribe the use of digital health services) as well as the public level (who will make up the user-base of digital health services). The activities will develop the core competencies required to achieve good dHL, but also to relate it to developments in society regarding health, digital technology use, civic engagement, and sociocultural and socioeconomic trends.

How IDE AHL addresses the main problems

Health literacy- and dHL-related literature has increased exponentially over the last half decade as awareness of its importance has grown. IDE AHL is therefore forming the foundation of its strategy through a comprehensive mapping of evaluated policies, studies, funded projects, and current practices in the EU and selected non-EU countries. This work is a major contribution to the understanding of what works in improving dHL. The results will also feed into the **Global Atlas of Literacies in Health (GALH), which will be upgraded into a continually updated, verified knowledge source for decision-makers and practitioners to freely access.**

Successful practices (so-called “champions”) and less successful interventions implemented in real-life settings (good practices) are often created and implemented separately. IDE AHL has **created a knowledge exchange network of those identified dHL practices across the EU and beyond (Network of Champions)** to facilitate the best performing practices as well as help improve those that may be underperforming.

The planned EU strategy for improving dHL will be co-created through over 100 workshops, exercises, and consultations involving more than 1,300 stakeholders identified by the IDE AHL consortium partners. These include representatives from policy makers, health care professionals, technology developers, academia, civil society organisations, citizens and the media.

IDEAHL

Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living

How IDE AHL addresses the main problems

The co-created strategy will point out several promising interventions, of **which some will be piloted by IDE AHL at the national and/or regional level**, their effects will be evaluated, and adjusted as necessary.

Current HL and dHL levels and trends in EU Member States will be obtained and presented in an online interactive Atlas, based on IDE AHL's mapping of literature.

IDE AHL suggest, that the choice of dHL measurement tools should be based on the context and the target group, and tools should be further validated among citizens in the EU countries. In particular, among young people and children.

These deliverables are still dependent on active stakeholder engagement to achieve real benefits. Knowledge sources, suggested strategies, policies, and interventions still need to be implemented by those in relevant positions to gain traction and have positive effects on dHL in different groups and locations.

Expected benefits

IDEAHL's outputs are designed to promote several advantageous developments in the EU Member States, including:

Adoption by citizens of healthier lifestyles, behaviours, and choices that lead to a longer, more independent and active life with a reduced disease burden - especially among vulnerable groups and stages of life.

Based on dHL practices, create better interaction between citizens and health care providers through improved monitoring and communication methods.

Improved trust and engagement with proven, effective digital health technologies at all ages, increasing adherence to health promotion and disease prevention interventions.

Improved and integrated dialogue and coordination between stakeholders and policy makers in developing more effective cross-sectoral dHL solutions for all.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

IDEAHL

Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living

1. Digital health literacy is a super determinant of healthy decision-making in a digitalized society. It must be addressed first and foremost, as the benefits and success of other digital health tools and services depends on it.

2. By 2024, the IDEAHL initiative will create an implementable, EU-wide strategy to enable use of dHL best practices and monitoring methods, using co-creation methods involving a wide range of stakeholders.

3. Successful implementation of the EU strategy will be largely dependent on the real commitment of policy- and decision-makers in the early stages of the strategy-forming process.

IDEAHL VALUE PROPOSITIONS

What you can do to get involved in the IDEAHL work

IDEAHL
Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living

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- Contact the IDEAHL consortium **leader** (martamaria.pisanogonzalez@asturias.org) who can help you get registered for upcoming stakeholder consultations in your country or nearby.
- Download the reports (<https://ideahl.eu>) from the initial knowledge maps regarding best practices and monitoring and evaluation methods.
- Use this white paper as a starter discussion point at your next meeting to raise awareness about what dHL is and how it affects your own work.

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ANNEX III - PARTICIPANTS

Name and Surname	Organization	Participation	co-creation session
Gabriele Mingolla	CEI		Yes
Gian Matteo Apuzzo	Central European Initiative		Yes
Stefania Silvestri	CEI-ES		No
Sara Amador	Consulta Europa		Yes
Michelle Perello	Consulta Europa		Yes
Beatrice Avagnina	Consulta Europa		Yes
Afonso Araújo	All Digital	In presence	Yes
ISABEL DIEZ VALCARCE	SESPA	In presence	Yes
Kai Schnnackenberg	Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs	In presence	Yes
Ahrendt, Roland	Affairs and Integration of the Free and	In presence	Yes
Laura Pruneda González	FICYT	Online	No
Petueli Tui Veremalumu	Border Health Protection Unit	Online	No
Iida AHONEN	EP	Online	No
Tania Cardona	Ministry for Health, Malta	Online	Yes
Inés Rey	FICYT	In presence	Yes
Marta Pisano	Coordination team	In presence	Yes
Cristina Fernández	SESPA-Coordination team	In presence	Yes
Mónica López Ventoso	Ministry of Health, Asturias, Spain.	In presence	Yes
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Dr. Katja Valkama	Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences	In presence	Yes
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Burga	ESAN	Online	Yes
Aleksandra Garbeva	Roche	Online	No
Borges Rodrigues	Nursing School f Lisbon	Online	Yes
Markens shllaku	Operator of Health Care Services - Albania	Online	No
Borges Rodrigues	Lisbon Nursing School	Online	Yes
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Maria Sotiriou	World Health Organization	In presence	No
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Derya öztomurcuk	Public Health department	Online	Yes
Sophie Matte	PATH	Online	No
Philippe Veltsos	PATH	Online	Yes
Scott Hughes	PATH	Online	No
Kieran Hannon	EY	Online	Yes
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Camille Dauvergne	European Medicines Agency	Online	No
Nancy De Jesus	Fédération Hospitalière de France	Online	Yes
Pavel Panayotov	Roche Bulgaria	Online	Yes
Maria José Rodríguez Carl	Pribcipality of Asturias Region	In presence	No
Agathe Larmor	E-Seniors	In presence	Yes
Vanessa Moore	European Institute of Women's Health	In presence	Yes
Seas Romane	E-Seniors	In presence	Yes
Cristina del Canto	Permanent Delegation of Castilla y León	In presence	No
Laura Chillerón	FCVRE - Generalitat Valenciana	In presence	No
Albert Royo	Delegation of Catalonia before the EU	In presence	No
Olga García	Delegation of Extremadura in Brussels	In presence	No
Patricia Nunez	Delegation of Extremadura in Brussels	In presence	No
Atiya Karim	Solutions4health	Online	Yes
Filiz Duyar Ağca	MoH, Ankara Provincial Health Directorate, Alt	Online	Yes
Marta Pisano González	Ministry of health Asturias	In presence	Yes
Luís Pinto	Crotalus Labs	Online	Yes
Stefan Buttigieg	Ministry for Health - Malta	Online	No
Joana Carvalho	Imperial College London	Online	No
Marilia Mariano	Bishop's University	Online	No
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Alberto Melon Fernandez	Crotalus Labs	Online	Yes
Cristiana Fernandes	Grupo Somos Saúde	Online	Yes
Ichlasul Amalia	Universitas Gadjah Mada	Online	No
Olga Navarro	UPV	Online	No
Stephan Schug	DGG German eHealth Association	Online	No
Eva Sabajova	NCZI	Online	No
Marcela Tırdea	Ministry of Health of the Republic of Moldova	Online	Yes

Sara Brazys	HaDEA	In presence	No
Laura Chillerón Ferrer	FCVRE - Generalitat Valenciana	In presence	No
Elena Alvarez Brasero	Delegation of Extremadura in Brussels	In presence	No
Nato Gzirishvili	Caucasus University	Online	No
Celia Alas Iglesias	IDEPA	In presence	Yes
Remedios Bordiu	Principado de Asturias	In presence	No
Rogério Ribeiro	APDP	Online	No
arnaud de ghellinck	WeTechCare	In presence	Yes
Adele De Stefani	ISRAA	In presence	Yes
Davide Tuis	ISRAA	In presence	Yes
Bárbara Barbosa	IPOP	Online	No
Paula Subirats	IATA-CSIC	In presence	No
Yasmina Saqqaa Acuña	Delegation of Andalusian Region in Brussels	In presence	No
Victor Solé	European Parliament	In presence	Yes
Anne McCusker	Belfast Healthy Cities	Online	Yes
George Antonakakis	European parliament	In presence	No
Ângela Sofia Silva Pinto	Cáritas Coimbra	In presence	Yes
Angel Barrera Nieto	Adiper	In presence	Yes
Pallavi Chatarajupalli	Hamburg university of Applied Sciences	Online	Yes
Andrea Čambalíková	Roche Slovakia	Online	No
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Dalia Coffetti	ENVI	Online	No
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Gaetano Paparella	Puglia Region - Aress	Online	No
Dragana Aleksic Matic	National consultant - UNICEF	Online	No
Sarah Wamala-Andersson	Mälardalens University	In presence	Yes
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Charlotte Brun Thorup	University collage Northern Denmark	In presence	Yes
Peggy Maguire	European Institute of Women's Health	Online	Yes
Chetan Sharma	WHO	Online	Yes
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Mariami Beridze	WHO	Online	No
Katre Trofimov	Ministry of Social Affairs, Estonia	Online	Yes
Lena schulze	Dr ansay	Online	Yes
John Kaswija	Mwanza College of Health and Allied Sciences	Online	Yes
Imma Buldu	Government of Catalonia. Representation to t	In presence	No
Lyudmila Niazyan	WHO	Online	Yes
Irene N Melamed	Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences, FLAC	Online	Yes
Rebecca Moore	EIWH	In presence	No
Cris Scotter	WHO	Online	Yes
David Novillo Ortiz	World Health Organization	In presence	No
Sofia Santos Nunes	Adiper	In presence	Yes
Angel Barrera Nieto	Adiper	In presence	Yes
Miljana Grbic	WHO	Online	No
Konstantinos KOTSIS	WHO ATHENS QUALITY OF CARE OFFICE	Online	No
Jenna Rautionaho	MEP Virkkunen office	In presence	No
Mika Uitto	SeAMK	In presence	Yes
Celia Alas Iglesias	IDEPA	In presence	Yes
Enrica Croda	Ca' Foscari University	Online	Yes
arnaud de ghellinck	wetechcare	In presence	Yes
Karin Schölin Bywall	Mälardalen University	In presence	Yes
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Isatou Sarr	Medical Research Council Unit The Gambia at	Online	Yes
Dimitrios Protogiros	Ministry of Health	Online	No
María Jesús de la Grana G	Private	In presence	Yes
Gabriela Irrazabal	RMIT University	In presence	Yes
Vania Putatti	EuroHealthNet	In presence	Yes
Mirko Claus	Personal	Online	No
Cristina Tecovich	Regione autonoma Friuli-Venezia Giulia	In presence	No
Silvia Trapa	Representation Office of Friuli-Venezia Giulia	In presence	Yes
Giuseppe Memola	AReSS Puglia	Online	No
Stefano De Monte	Cluster Life Sciences	Online	No
Aki Ishiwa	Region Emilia-Romagna	Online	No

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ANNEX IV - PICTURES

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